

Defining Victimhood: The Exclusion of People with Disabilities in Post-War Justice in Germany

BROOKLYN HORTENSTINE

Incoming PhD Candidate, Northwestern University in Evanston, Illinois

Abstract

In 1984, in response to petitions to recognise victims of euthanasia and people who were sterilised under Nazi laws for the purposes of reparations, the German Federal Minister of Finance declared that the requests were being denied because they were not repealed by the Allies, “had role models in foreign states” and “violated neither natural law nor rule of law.” This statement sparked a debate that had only made small steps in improvement after many of the surviving victims died and was never fully settled. This paper examines the intricacies of German post-war justice for people with disabilities through policies of reparations for sterilisation victims and the families of euthanasia victims. Because the Western Allied powers deemed the sterilisation law a measure of public health, most of the victims of the 1933 sterilisation law never saw an apology or responsibility taken by the German government for their ailments. Additionally, families of people who were killed under ‘euthanasia’ were excluded with the simple explanation that it was impossible to give reparations to people who were dead, and they did not qualify for simply being related. While these issues were addressed in some ways, they were never treated with the same regard as victims in other categories. This research is based not only on German laws concerning the treatment and reparations of Holocaust victims but also on stories shared by both victims of sterilisation and the surviving families of those who were victims of euthanasia, pulled from German newspapers, mostly from the 1980s, as well as other publications and stories which were shared. Attention will be paid both to West and East Germany, though it should be noted that the paper will focus mostly on West Germany, as the East refused to compensate victims for most of its history. A very brief history of sterilisation policies in the Allied nations will also be in order to explain their conclusions, but it will by no means be the focus of this paper. While scholars have addressed the lack of compensation before, my paper will stress these measures as a long history of a lack of disability rights.

Keywords: Reparations – Post-war Germany – People with Disabilities – Sterilisation – Euthanasia

Introduction

In the aftermath of the Second World War, the international community set out to prosecute the crimes committed by Nazi Germany, a task that required definitions of the extent of the crimes, of victims and perpetrators. While these categories remain delicate and elusive at best among historians of the Holocaust, they were necessary to deliver justice to the victims of the Holocaust, despite the many flaws that became apparent over time. Historians have spent decades trying to redefine and sort out the intricacies of the Nuremberg Trials and other trials concerning crimes that were committed while the Nazis were in power.¹ However, despite the ongoing attention, certain groups of victims remained largely unacknowledged and were denied justice in post-war Germany. Victims of sterilisation, and the families of those killed through ‘euthanasia’ are some of the most excluded groups in this case, and global acceptance of the legalisation of coerced sterilisation kept the German government from making amends until most of the survivors in these categories had died. Ultimately, the case for sterilised victims and the children of euthanasia victims shows that Germany, along with the rest of the world, was unwilling to dismantle their ableist prejudices and rehabilitate medical ethics even in the wake of the Holocaust.² This article examines post-war justice first by discussing the definitions of genocide and crimes against humanity agreed upon by the Allied powers and their effect on the legality of the 1933 sterilisation law, before turning to international efforts to receive reparations from West Germany, the stance of East Germany in the compensation debate with international organisations, and finally requests made by citizens on the individual level on behalf of themselves or their families.

Background

To properly explain the ease at which global communities dismissed sterilisation in the Nazi case, an understanding of eugenics in the wider twentieth century is crucial. As wider historiography shows, the practice of controlling a population to prevent social decline was a defining factor of the twentieth century. Coined in 1883 by Francis Galton, the term “eugenics” is derived from the Greek word for “wellborn.” It sought to create a scientific method for ensuring the biological fitness of a society. Galton and his supporters believed that physical, mental, and even moral traits of human beings could be controlled genetically, and severely discounted the role of one’s

¹ For a concise history of post-war trials and debates by and large see Mary Fulbrook, *Reckonings: Legacies of Nazi Persecution and the Quest for Justice*, (New York: Oxford University Press, 2020). For a deeper focus on crimes committed in hospitals and against people with disabilities, see Michael S. Bryant, *Confronting the “Good Death:” Nazi Euthanasia on Trial, 1945-1953* (Boulder: University Press of Colorado, 2005).

² Ableism refers to prejudice held against people because of their disabilities.

environment and circumstances.³ While the concept of eugenics emerged at the end of the nineteenth century, it was not until the twentieth century that nations began to view eugenics as something to be implemented on a wide scale.

Eugenic practices can be divided into two broader categories: positive eugenics and negative eugenics. Positive eugenics refers to a particular emphasis on fostering the reproduction of the most ‘fit’ members of society.⁴ In its purest form, positive eugenics does not promote strategies that work against minority groups that might be considered ‘undesirable.’ Examples of positive eugenics include, but are not limited to, the use of *in vitro* fertilisation, artificial insemination, and the development of sperm banks.⁵ These procedures are most commonly associated with current discussions on fertility, but the ideas behind them began developing as early as the 1930s. Despite these concepts occupying the minds of scholars as a possibility, the lack of technology meant that in the twentieth century, the practices of positive eugenics alone remained an ideal rather than a reality to the world.⁶

By contrast, negative eugenics were policies put in place to control the reproduction of “those individuals who are so meagrely or defectively endowed by nature that their offspring are bound to be antisocial, or at least unable to care for themselves.”⁷ This definition did not explicitly include everyone with a disability, nor did it directly exclude others, but it made it clear that being “anti-social” and defying the norms set forth by society would be treated as a disability itself. In some ways, it even implies that living a lifestyle outside of what was deemed *normal* is a larger disability than the inability to care for oneself. Unlike positive eugenics, negative eugenics did not rely on science too complex for its time and thus became the dominant model that proved successful in eugenic pursuits. It relied on forced sterilisation via vasectomy or tubal ligation, processes that were established at the end of the nineteenth century.⁸

Eugenic policies were implemented in numerous countries throughout the twentieth century, and while it would be reductionist to say that Nazi Germany was inspired by one nation in particular, German and American collaboration in the movement is notable. For example, prominent eugenicist Charles Davenport, who was one of the leading proponents for compulsory sterilisation in the United States, collaborated heavily with German eugenicists at the time. In the

³ Mark B. Adams, ed., *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*, Monographs on the History and Philosophy of Biology (New York: Oxford University Press, 1990), 3.

⁴ Maurizio Meloni, “Into the Wild: The Radical Ethos of Eugenics,” in *Political Biology: Science and Social Values in Human Heredity from Eugenics to Epigenetics* (London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2016), 64–92.

⁵ Meloni, 71.

⁶ Meloni, “Into the Wild,” 70–71.

⁷ Harry H. Laughlin, “The Relation of Eugenics to Other Sciences,” *The Eugenics Review* 11, no. 2 (1919): 53–64, quoted in Meloni, 71.

⁸ Meloni, 71.

1920s, the United States passed some of the most widespread sterilisation laws on state levels, which were upheld by the Supreme Court in 1927. American genetic societies were the leaders, scholarly and financially, for the global eugenics movement.⁹ Leading American funders like the Rockefeller and Carnegie Institutes were known to fund German eugenicists with the equivalent of millions of dollars.¹⁰ Additionally, membership in the International Federation of Eugenic Organizations (IFEEO) allowed German scholars access to research, articles, and legislation on the practices of eugenics worldwide.¹¹ Through their exchange of information, German eugenicists no doubt became familiar with America's system of documenting familial illnesses through the establishment of the Eugenics Record Office as well as the difficulties faced by their American colleagues when implementing eugenic practices on both state and federal levels.¹²

In 1933, Hitler passed the Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring, commonly referred to as the Nazi sterilisation law or simply the 1933 sterilisation law. The new legislation legalised nationwide sterilisation performed by surgeons if “following the experience of medical science, it may be expected with great probability that their offspring may suffer severe physical or mental hereditary impairment.”¹³ Disabilities that fell under this category included schizophrenia, “feeble-mindedness,” Huntington's disease, epilepsy, “insanity,” hereditary blindness, and hereditary deafness. People who could propose sterilisation included the patient themselves, a legal guardian, a doctor, a psychiatrist, or a director of a health or living institution, but the final decision rested with hereditary health courts who would review the case and vote for or against the procedure.¹⁴

The addition of hereditary health courts and the strict implementation on a national level suggest a level of American influence, but the insistence that Nazi-Germany simply adopted American laws is greatly exaggerated. The Nazis may have drawn off American failures in eugenics and curated their list of disabilities from Laughlin's “Model Sterilisation Law,” but the law itself was drawn mainly from the sterilisation law drafted by a committee of the Prussian Health Board in 1932.¹⁵ Regardless of its level of direct and traceable influence, American and German

⁹ Edwin Black, *War against the Weak: Eugenics and America's Campaign to Create a Master Race* (New York: Four Walls Eight Windows, 2003), 272–77.

¹⁰ Black, 284. In 1923 alone, the Rockefeller Foundation funded German scientists with \$410,000, amounting to about 4 million in the twenty-first century.

¹¹ Black, 280–83. Membership to the society was organisational. A multitude of German Kaiser Wilhelm Institutes were active in the IFEEO, most notably the Kaiser Wilhelm Institute for Psychiatry, the Institute for Anthropology, Human Hereditary, and Eugenics, and the Institute for Brain Research.

¹² Egbert Klautke, “The Germans Are Beating Us at Our Own Game: American Eugenics and the German Sterilization Law of 1933,” *History of the Human Sciences* 29, no. 3 (July 2016): 25–43, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952695116631230>.

¹³ Klautke, 32.

¹⁴ Klautke, 32.

¹⁵ Klautke, 31.

eugenicists largely continued to support one another despite slowly changing attitudes regarding sterilisation. Both nations used the support of the other to justify their practices.¹⁶ American Joseph S. DeJarnette, a proponent for sterilisation and superintendent of the Western Virginia Hospital, even complained that “the Germans are beating us at our own game.”¹⁷ Further, America’s position in the eugenics movement would be used to justify the existence of the 1933 sterilisation law in the post-war period, becoming a significant source of difficulty for people seeking justice and reparations. The legality of American sterilisation was also used as a point of defence, albeit unsuccessfully, for Karl Brandt and his fellow defendants at the Doctor’s Trial in Nuremberg in 1947.¹⁸

Literature Review and Methods

Work on disabled people in the Holocaust began emerging in the 1990s, and the topic of sterilisation is most often studied in conjunction with the Nazi euthanasia program, often referred to by its code name, the T4 Program. Perhaps the most ground-breaking historian on the topic of disability in Nazi Germany is Henry Friedlander. In his book *The Origins of Nazi Genocide: From Euthanasia to the Final Solution* (1995), Friedlander asserts, against the historiography of his time, that people with disabilities were not only victims of Nazi oppression, but that Hitler’s campaign against disabled people provided a “test case” for the methods used in the Final Solution. Friedlander’s stance that people with disabilities do qualify as victims of the Holocaust, and are one of the first victims, has become widely accepted in Holocaust research and in many ways laid the groundwork for the historical study of disabled people in Nazi Germany at a time when disabled people were not considered in scholarship more broadly, either.¹⁹ Published a year earlier in 1994, Michael Burleigh’s work, *Death and Deliverance: 'Euthanasia' in Germany, c.1900 to 1945* followed the idea of the “mercy death” throughout German history, placing the concept of ‘euthanasia’ in a wider range of German historiography.

These historians were instrumental in bringing the oppression of disabled people to the realm of Holocaust Studies, but their works focus on the programs themselves rather than the legal implications in the aftermath of the Holocaust and people seeking reparations. For this, Ernst

¹⁶ Klautke, 27, 35-37.

¹⁷ Klautke, 26.

¹⁸ Klautke, 37.

¹⁹ The debate on whether disabled people are considered victims of the Holocaust was part of a larger debate on expanding Holocaust research to other groups, including Roma people. Friedlander’s most notable critic was Yehuda Bauer. See, for example, Yehuda Bauer and Sybil Milton. “Correspondence: ‘Gypsies and the Holocaust.’” *The History Teacher* 25, no. 4 (1992): 513–21. <https://doi.org/10.2307/494357>.

Klee,²⁰ Paul Weidling,²¹ Michael S. Bryant,²² and Margret Hamm²³ have done significant research to document the actions of medical personnel and the post-war legal processes. Their achievements cannot be understated, but they either focus mainly on reparations for Jewish victims of the Holocaust (in the case of Weidling) or have chronicled post-war justice strictly in West Germany (in the case of Klee, Bryant, and Hamm.)

This article provides a more comprehensive look at post-war justice by examining the issue of reparations in both West and East Germany, as well as the lasting effects and problems in Germany after reunification. By beginning with the debates surrounding the definitions of crimes against humanity and genocide at Nuremberg, analysing legal proceedings in the Bundestag, official communication between advocacy groups and government officials, the process of denazification, and first-hand accounts from survivors seeking reparations, this article reconstructs the complications of post-war justice specifically for disabled victims of National Socialism. At the same time, it pays attention to the details of post-war policy in both sectors of influence in Germany during and after the occupation and acknowledges the most recent actions concerning the ongoing issue of compensation in Germany. Moreover, it discusses not just the failure of Germany in this regard, but also places some responsibility on the Allied powers and the general attitude towards people with disabilities at this time around the world.

A Note on "Disability" during National Socialism

When referring to "disability" and "disabled people," this article relies on the classifications placed on individuals by the Nazi state. While these labels are dangerous, it is both impossible and impractical to try to trace the validity of someone's disability at this time, especially as labels of "idiocy," "feeble-mindedness," and "insanity" among others are now obsolete and hold no concrete definitions.²⁴ As such, this article assumes that those sterilised under the Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring were, in one way or another, deemed disabled by the Nazi state. The same assumption is made when discussing citizens who were institutionalised in homes for people with disabilities, hospitals, or other residential care centres. Based on legal criteria, people

²⁰ Ernst Klee, *Was sie taten, was sie wurden: Ärzte, Juristen und andere Beteiligte am Kranken- oder Judenmord* (Frankfurt am Main: Fischer Taschenbuch, 1986). Klee also authored numerous articles for the German newspaper *Die Zeit* on crimes against the disabled during Nazi times.

²¹ Paul Weidling, ed., *From Clinic to Concentration Camp: Reassessing Nazi Medical and Racial Research, 1933–1945* (London: Routledge, 2017).

²² Michael S. Bryant, *Confronting the "Good Death": Nazi Euthanasia on Trial, 1945–1953* (Boulder, Colorado: University Press of Colorado, 2005).

²³ Margret Hamm, ed., *Ausgegrenzt! warum? Zwangssterilisierte und Geschädigte der NS-"Euthanasie" in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (Berlin: Metropol, 2017).

²⁴ For more on the history of this terminology, see John Simpson, "Chapter 2: What's in a Name?," in *Supporting Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities & Mental Illness*, eds. Sherri Melrose et al. (Vancouver: BCCampus, 2015), 8–18.

sterilised under the Nazi sterilisation law were documented as having “feeble-mindedness,” schizophrenia, hereditary epilepsy, manic-depressive disorder, hereditary deafness, hereditary blindness, “severe malformation,” severe alcoholism, and Huntington’s Disease. Of these classifications, a diagnosis of “feeble-mindedness” constituted more than half of the sterilisations performed in 1934.²⁵

Similarly, children and adults with more severe disabilities such as “idiocy,” Down’s Syndrome, paralysis, Cerebral Palsy, and major deformities, among others, were killed through the Nazi “euthanasia” program.²⁶ These victims were deemed “lives unworthy of life.” This designation was lifted from attorney Karl Binding and psychiatrist Alfred Hoche’s book *Permitting the Destruction of Life Unworthy of Life* (1920).²⁷ It was distorted by Nazi propaganda to describe people considered useless, non-contributing members of National Socialist society. The original document contained notable differences from Nazi policy, such as the insistence of consent from a patient or a guardian when considering euthanasia, but the phrase is now synonymous with Nazism.²⁸

It is important to acknowledge the arbitrary and dangerous nature of these terms and to recognise that despite these guidelines, many people sterilised or killed under these laws would not have been or considered themselves disabled. However, it would cause far more confusion and be extremely problematic to redefine disability in this article. Therefore, distinctions between victim groups who received reparations are only made when it is abundantly clear that the German government is classifying a group as not having been sterilised based on disability for the purposes of determining compensation. Additionally, most of the personal stories throughout this article do not specify a survivor’s disability. This was not a deliberate choice, but rather because many survivors do not comment on their conditions, whether legitimate or perceived by the Nazi regime.²⁹

²⁵ Henry Friedlander, *The Origins of Nazi Genocide: From Euthanasia to the Final Solution* (Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press, 1995), 29.

²⁶ Friedlander, 45.

²⁷ Karl Binding and Alfred Hoche, *Die Freigabe der Vernichtung lebensunwerten Lebens: ihr Mass und ihr Ziel* (1920) (Berlin: Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag, 2006).

²⁸ Howard Brody and M. Wayne Cooper, “Binding and Hoche’s ‘Life Unworthy of Life’: A Historical and Ethical Analysis,” *Perspectives in Biology and Medicine* 57, no. 4 (2014): 500–511, <https://doi.org/10.1353/pbm.2014.0042>.

²⁹ For more on National Socialist notions of disability, see Staffan Bengtsson, “The Nation’s Body: Disability and Deviance in the Writings of Adolf Hitler,” *Disability & Society* 33, no. 3 (March 16, 2018): 416–32, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2018.1423955>.

Genocide and Crimes Against Humanity at Nuremberg

Any discussion of victimhood and genocide must begin in the place where definitions for genocide were first evoked to describe crime: at the Nuremberg Trials. The failure to consider disabled people, particularly those sterilised through the Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring, as victims of Nazi persecution lies largely with the Allied Powers and the restrictions put in place with the prosecution of Nazi criminals.³⁰ The way in which Nazi criminals should be prosecuted in the post-war era became a point of contention. Where Raphael Lemkin clearly expressed a desire for the concept of “genocide” to apply to crimes against groups of humans as broadly as possible, and for the prosecutions of the Nuremberg trials to encompass crimes that took place beginning in 1933 until the end of the war, the Allies used the word in a more limited sense. Sir Hartley Shawcross, who served as the main prosecutor for the British at Nuremberg, agreed that “genocide” was a crime against humanity that was exacerbated to the most extreme extent. However, he also inserted that for a crime to be considered genocide in the case of the Nazis, it had to be committed in connection with the war itself.³¹ This decision was part of a larger effort of reaching a compromise between the Allied Powers on exactly who the charges could be applied to in the post-war era and to what extent.

The biggest challenge facing the lawmakers behind the International Military Tribunal was the wording of Article 6 of the Nuremberg Charter. The charter itself was a collection of laws that would be used to prosecute Nazis, and Article 6 defined the bounds of the Tribunal and the charges of crimes against peace, war crimes, and crimes against humanity.³² Initially, Soviet representatives proposed a draft of international laws that would attach the criminality of waging aggressive wars specifically to instances where it was done “specifically on behalf of the European Axis powers.”³³ Without the distinction, they felt that the laws they drafted could potentially be used against the Allies for the extreme actions taken in their defensive measures. American delegates insisted that the laws they created had to be able to apply to any future nations who might break international law. Thus, they rejected the revision because it meant that by definition,

³⁰ The terms “disabled people” and “people with disabilities” are used interchangeably throughout this article. The author recognises the ongoing conversation about the usage of these terms and acknowledges the arguments made for the usage of both terms with no ill intent. For more information, see Krista L. Best et al., “Language Matters! The Long-Standing Debate between Identity-First Language and Person First Language,” *Assistive Technology* 34, no. 2 (March 4, 2022): 127–28, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400435.2022.2058315>.

³¹ Philippe Sands, *East West Street: On the Origins of “Genocide” and “Crimes against Humanity,”* (New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 2016), 334–36.

³² ICRC Database, Treaties, States Parties and Commentaries, “Agreement for the Prosecution and Punishment of the Major War Criminals of the European Axis, and Charter of the International Military Tribunal.” (London, August 8, 1945.) Article 6, <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/nuremberg-tribunal-charter-1945/article-6b>.

³³ Francine Hirsch, *Soviet Judgment at Nuremberg: A New History of the International Military Tribunal after World War II* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2020), 68.

the charges could only be applied to specific nations. Instead, American negotiator and Supreme Court judge Robert Jackson suggested that the preamble to Article 6 could establish the tribunal's jurisdiction as "on behalf of the European Axis powers."³⁴ By adding the limitations to the preamble rather than the definition itself, the Soviets received the protection they asked for without the problem of the Charter not being able to be applied to other countries in the future if needed.

At the same time, Jackson stood firm in his assertion that "crimes against humanity" had to be in connection with the crime of aggressive war, noting "regrettable circumstances" faced by minorities in his own country at the time. Soviet and British delegates supported Jackson against rejections from the French representative in this particular matter, but the Soviets remained doubtful that a preamble would protect them.³⁵ In the end, compromises were made. Jackson became less persistent that "aggression" had to be defined as a key distinction with other kinds of warfare, the Soviet delegation accepted that declaring jurisdiction be separate from legal definitions, and the French agreed to allow a restrictive definition of crimes against humanity that placed it dependent on both the timeline of the war and in connection to other crimes. These stipulations would prevail at Nuremberg. The implication, of course, was that any crimes committed before the invasion of Poland in September 1939 did not fall within the jurisdiction of the Nuremberg Tribunals.

In addition to the timeline, distinctions between genocide and crimes against humanity are at play. Initially, Lemkin wanted genocide to encompass crimes that aimed to destroy groups of human beings as broadly as possible in order to maximise the probability of delivering justice to as many victim groups of the Holocaust as possible. However, this was not the case, and the charge of genocide was employed sparingly during the Nuremberg trials.³⁶ Much more commonly used was Hersch Lauterpacht's term, "crimes against humanity."³⁷ Lauterpacht was a British international human rights lawyer who, like Lemkin, was personally affected by the Holocaust. Throughout the 1930s, he had already written many books on international law. "Crimes against humanity" importantly differed from "genocide" in that it stressed the importance of protecting the individual over the group. The idea was meant not only to protect people who may not fit under a defined group that was necessary for the charge of genocide to be applied, but it also stressed that individual criminals could be responsible for acts committed in the name of the state. For all the debate the distinction caused, the charge of crimes against humanity prevented the

³⁴ Hirsch, 70.

³⁵ Hirsch, 70.

³⁶ Sands, 335-336.

³⁷ Sands, 3-4.

Nazis on trial from being able to claim that they were not individually responsible for their own crimes because they were working on orders given by Hitler.

These two conditions, while they left plenty of room for the persecution of criminals who acted against defined victim groups—Jews, Poles, etc.—opened a door for the exclusion of disabled people. For one, the *Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring* was not considered a crime at all, as it was passed before 1939. While sterilisation was considered as an issue during the trials, and was later considered an aspect of genocide itself, the sterilisations considered at the trial were those that were conducted to destroy a racial, religious, or ethnic group in concentration camps, or the experimentation that often occurred alongside it as the Nazis attempted to create new scientific methods for the procedure. Sterilisations that happened outside the scope of the war were assumed to be against those who were considered disabled, and were not considered a crime in their own right, as nations reserved the right to pass sterilisation laws as a matter of routine public health.³⁸ Both of these considerations formed the basis under which Germany would justify excluding people with disabilities from the definition of who would be considered a victim of the Holocaust.

Legalities of Victimhood and Compensation in the Federal Republic of Germany

Despite the conditions set at Nuremberg, the Federal Act on Compensation for Victims of National Socialist Persecution (BEG) of 1953 passed in West Germany was intended to compensate a wider group of people, by offering compensation to all eligible groups who were targeted from January 1933 to May 1945.³⁹ However, under this law, people persecuted due to their disabilities were still not clearly considered victims of Nazi persecution. As per section one of the Federal Act on Compensation for Victims of National Socialist Persecution (BEG) of 1953, victims of National Socialism are classified as those who have suffered for “reasons of political opposition to National Socialism or for reasons of race, faith or belief and have suffered damage to life, body, health, freedom, property, assets, or in their professional or economic progress.”⁴⁰ In most cases, this included the surviving relatives of the victims and those who were injured by the Nazis for opposition against them as defined under §1, paragraphs one and two, quoted above.

³⁸ For more information on eugenic sterilisations in other countries, see Mark B. Adams, *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1990), and Edwin Black, *War Against the Weak: America's Campaign to Create a Master Race* (New York: Four Walls Eight Windows, 2003).

³⁹ Bundesministerium der Justiz and Bundesamt für Justiz, “Bundesgesetz zur Entschädigung für Opfer der Nationalsozialistischen Verfolgung (Bundesentschädigungsgesetz - BEG)” (1953).

⁴⁰ “Bundesentschädigungsgesetz.”

Because disabled people were not listed explicitly as victims in these paragraphs, their families were often unable to claim reparations as well. Some succeeded via a revision passed in 1965 under §171, paragraph 4, no. 2, which stated that monetary compensation could be granted if it was reasonable to assume that the surviving dependent would be financially supported by the person who was killed if they were alive today. This, of course, was not possible for many when considering “life unworthy of life,” as the very reason for their persecution was their presumed inability to contribute to the nation economically.

The issue of compensation for people sterilised during the Nazi regime was broached in the Bundestag multiple times during the post-war era. In 1957 during parliamentary session 191 in Bonn, the discussion was driven mainly by the remarks of Heinrich Ritzel, a member of the Socialist Party of Germany (SPD) and Alfred Hartmann, a member of the Christian Social Union in Bavaria (CSU).⁴¹ Hartmann served as the state secretary of the Federal Ministry of Finance at the time, the legislative body responsible for handling compensation claims.⁴² When the question of compensation for those sterilised was raised, Hartmann responded by dividing the group of “sterilised people” into three groups: those who were sterilised because of their race, faith, or beliefs as outlined by the Compensation Law, those who were sterilised through unapproved methods, and those who were sterilised through approved methods because they were perceived as disabled under the Nazi state. Hartmann made it clear that when it came to sterilisation, the Bundestag specifically singled out the third group, those sterilised under the Law for Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring and denied them the possibility of receiving payments.⁴³

At this session, Hartmann gave four main reasons for the Bundestag’s refusal to compensate disabled victims of National Socialism. First, they continually argued that other countries had their own sterilisation laws in place, for example, the United States and Sweden.⁴⁴ While this point is certainly true, as Ritzel points out, the countries listed as justification never employed forced sterilisation as strictly or widespread as Nazi Germany had done. For example, between 1941 and 1976, approximately 63,000 people in Sweden were sterilised. In the United States, by 1960 approximately 61,540 people were sterilised under the law.⁴⁵ While none of these

⁴¹ This is a regional sister party of the Christian Democratic Union of Germany (CDU). The CSU operates only in Bavaria, while the CDU operates in the other German states.

⁴² From 1923–35 Hartmann served as senior governing council in the Ministry of Finance. Because he refused to join the Nazi party, he was first transferred to the tax office Berlin-Friedrichshain from 1935–1942, and then to the Federal Audit Court, where he was responsible for managing the special property tax on Jews, before being drafted in 1944. See Muzinger Internationales Biographisches Archiv 47/1967 (November 13, 1967.)

⁴³ “2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung. Bonn, Donnerstag, den 7. Februar 1957” (Deutscher Bundestag, 1957).

⁴⁴ “2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung.”

⁴⁵ Stephanie Hyatt, “A Shared History of Shame: Sweden’s Four-Decade Policy of Forced Sterilization and the Eugenics Movement in the United States,” *Indiana International & Comparative Law Review* 8, no. 2 (1998): 475–503.

countries demonstrate morally ethical medical practices, to compare them to the 400.000 people sterilised in Nazi Germany between the years of 1933 and 1945 explicitly dismisses the extreme intention and ideology held by Nazi Germany. When Ritzel brought this point up, Hartmann had no other explanations. He could not say for sure that the Bundestag representatives knew this or had taken it into consideration, and simply pressed further that no additional action was to be taken.

Hartmann continues by saying that, in addition to precedent, the Federal Compensation Act does not apply to non-material issues, except for when one's liberty is infringed upon. He insisted that sterilisation on its own does no physical damage to someone, and when done correctly only has the possibility of psychological damage, concluding this particular point by implying that this risk does not matter because, in the case of disabled people, those who were sterilised under the 1933 law were "essentially already mentally unstable."⁴⁶ In the fourth point, Hartmann encouraged people to file general claims of their sterilisations as "sacrifices" or to file claims for damages made during the sterilisation procedure when applicable, of which both options remained largely out of reach and defeated the goal of gaining recognition for those individuals and organisations who wished for sterilisation survivors to be added to the criteria of victims of National Socialism.⁴⁷ His motives for this denial on a personal level are unclear, as he continued to repeat that the Bundestag had no intentions or desires to pass further compensation acts, repeatedly citing that they had no obligation to do so because the sterilisation law of 1933 was in line with the laws of other nations at the time, and not an act of war.

The points raised by Hartmann would be repeated a multitude of times when post-war Germany repeatedly revisited the issue of compensation for forced sterilisation. The solidity of the argument as well as the people involved in it often raises questions about Germany's true commitment to making amends with the past. For example, the discussion resurfaced in 1961, when a group of lawmakers and seven "experts" in the fields of medicine and genetics met to discuss the possibility of expanding reparations and repealing the sterilisation law. Three of the seven people invited to give their professional opinions were former Nazi doctors who had supported the sterilisation law under Hitler. The biases that would obviously come with them seemed to be of minimal concern for the group, which ultimately decided once again that sterilisation ordered by hereditary health courts did not violate any international laws. Their reasoning was based again on the presence of sterilisation in other countries, and the fact that the Allies found the law constitutional during occupation because it was in line with the laws of other

⁴⁶ "2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung," 1087, section B.

⁴⁷ "2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung," 1087, section B.

nations at the time.⁴⁸ While true, this logic ignores the fact that sterilisation in Nazi Germany took place at an unprecedented rate in comparison to other nations.

Because of the widespread legitimisation of coerced sterilisation, compensation for victims was championed, for the most part, not as a mass group effort, but more commonly as smaller feats by individual organisations representing specific groups, often within their respective countries. For example, a French survivor's organisation, *Association nationale des anciennes déportées et internées de la Résistance*, succeeded in gaining the support of the UN in 1950, leading to the passing of an action that ordered Germany to issue reparations to women survivors of concentration camp experiments. While the compensation for sterilisation victims is minimal (around 3,000 DM), it is a notable achievement in comparison to the efforts made and attention gained by *the* League of Persons Damaged by "Euthanasia" and Compulsory Sterilisation (Bund der "Euthanasie"-Geschaedigten und Zwangssterilisierten, BEZ). This organisation, which tries to include all victims, even those whose sterilisations were deemed "routine," was not established until 1987, and had most of its attempts to obtain reparations for all rejected.⁴⁹

Highlighting the success of other groups in comparison to BEZ is not to suggest that victims sterilised outside of the confines of the Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring had an easy time obtaining reparations after the war. They, too, often received small payouts that did not make a significant impact. Many survivors who were sterilised using reversible techniques campaigned for the reversal to be attempted, and for the costs incurred to fall on the government. Their requests remained ignored despite having been offered as a genuine way for the German government to make amends without the need for continuous reparations.⁵⁰ Still, it is clear that international advocacy groups did not attempt, or at least were not as successful in their campaigns for disabled survivors, or the families of those subject to euthanasia.

Compensation for victims of sterilisation came slowly and was not uniformly based on the situation of the victim in question. From 1953 onwards, German sterilisation victims attempted to file claims as general victims of Nazi persecution but were given a plethora of reasons for rejection. The first revisions for payments made specifically to victims of coerced sterilisation were not established until 1980 under §171, paragraph four of the reparation regulations. This change was made only after pressure from victims and international groups forced German authorities to accept that Nazi-era sterilisations were criminal acts. However, this addition had notable

⁴⁸ "Protokoll der 34. Sitzung des Ausschusses für Wiedergutmachung," (Bonn: Deutscher Bundestag, April 13, 1961).

⁴⁹ Paul Weindling, "Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization," in *Psychiatry and the Legacies of Eugenics: Historical Studies of Alberta and Beyond*, eds. Frank W. Stahnisch and Erna Kurbegović (Edmonton: Athabasca University Press, 2020), 181-98.

⁵⁰ Weindling, "Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization," 188.

differences from the compensation laws passed previously. While the general applications that many filed in 1953 would have allowed survivors to receive payments for the rest of their lives as others had received, the program launched in 1980 allowed only a one-time payment of 5,000 DM.⁵¹ In 1988, this was extended to include a monthly payment of 100 DM, and in 1999 adjusted and increased to 120 Euros after the currency change.⁵² Today, this amount has been adjusted to a maximum payment of 2.556 Euros total.⁵³

Two-Sided Responsibility? Reparations and the Medical Sphere in the German Democratic Republic

The measures discussed in this article thus far concern only the actions taken either by the Allies in Germany as an occupied nation, or the responsibility taken by the Federal Republic after 1949. Despite the Soviet sphere being the only occupation zone to outlaw the sterilisation law under the pretence that it harboured antidemocratic and Nazi spirit, relatively little was done both concerning compensating victims of the Holocaust and putting an end to proponents for eugenic sterilisation.

Until the very end of its existence, East Germany rejected any responsibility for the crimes of the Holocaust, insisting that the people who were involved in the creation of the new State were anti-fascist and that East Germany was the 'rightful' Germany after the war. When faced with the discussion of reparations to any individuals or the State of Israel more broadly, the GDR continually cited that their obligations were only those agreed upon at Yalta (February 1945) and Potsdam (July 1945), which covered only reparations to be made by Germany to Allied nations.⁵⁴ As such, East German reparations came only in the form of investment and consumer goods that were shipped to the Soviet Union, such as machinery, sugar, and household chemicals.⁵⁵ East Germany did not reach any agreements for reparations towards the Holocaust until 1990, after the country's first and only democratic election as an independent nation. During this time, East Germany issued apologies for its continued refusal to cooperate with organisations that sought reparations and began acknowledging that it had a responsibility towards victims. However, even after this breakthrough, the East German government conducted agreements solely with the

⁵¹ "Wiedergutmachung - Regelungen zur Entschädigung von NS-Unrecht" (Bundesministerium der Finanzen, May 10, 2022), article no. BMF40106.

⁵² Weindling, "Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization," 193-95.

⁵³ "Wiedergutmachung."

⁵⁴ Angelika Timm, *Jewish Claims Against East Germany* (Budapest: Central European University Press, 1998), 73-94.

⁵⁵ John P. Nettl, "Soviet Reparations Policy," in *The Eastern Zone and Soviet Policy in Germany, 1945-50* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1951), 199-238.

World Jewish Congress (WJC), speaking only of their commitment to Jewish victims of the Holocaust with no mention of further victim categories.⁵⁶

After reunification, Germany further addressed the lack of responsibility taken by the GDR through a series of updates and revisions made to their reparations law. In the added statements, the newly unified Germany claimed that in the GDR, victims of National Socialism received benefits such as general health care and pensions, both for their old age and for their status as survivors of Nazi tyranny, and “honour pensions.” These benefits were only paid to residents of the GDR, but no further details as to what the payments were or who was classified as a victim in these cases were explicitly given, beyond that they likely only went to those who were ‘viewed favourably’ by the socialist system. The same addition makes clear that separate restitution agreements were made between East Germany and the governments of Austria, Denmark, Finland, and Sweden for survivors who were residents of those nations, but again, no other defining details are given.⁵⁷ Survivors living in East Germany were only eligible to apply for reparations under BEG after reunification. They were also granted the opportunity to apply for restitution of property, an option that remained open to them until 1992 (real estate) and 1993 (movable property).⁵⁸ Despite the constant revisions given to the law, disabled people continued to have difficulty obtaining recognition because they were not added to the class of victims. The ability to open reparation claims again for East Germans because they were previously ineligible illustrates that the exclusion of disabled victims was done by choice, rather than need or circumstance.

Even though sterilisation was outlawed in East Germany, not everyone was in favour of such a move. Opinions on the matter remained mixed, and while no sterilisations took place, professionals in the country were certainly products of their time and some undoubtedly viewed sterilisation as a public health measure, even if they considered themselves anti-fascist. On the other hand, we also cannot assume that medical professionals in East Germany were vehemently anti-Nazi. Despite being regarded as the zone with the strictest denazification protocols, the medical sphere is one area in which relative leniency was shown.⁵⁹ Typically, a person’s job was not the first consideration made by the denazification commissions, but in the case of those in medical care and social work, this was a factor often put above someone’s political past. While this

⁵⁶ Ari L. Goldman, “Upheaval in the East: East Germany; East Germany Agrees to Pay Reparations to the Jewish Victims of the Nazis,” *The New York Times*, February 9, 1990. See also Ferdinand Protzman, “Upheaval in the East; The East Germans Issue an Apology for Nazi Crimes,” *The New York Times*, April 13, 1990.

⁵⁷ “Wiedergutmachung,” section 1.5.

⁵⁸ “Wiedergutmachung.”

⁵⁹ Timothy R. Vogt, *Denazification in Soviet-Occupied Germany: Brandenburg, 1945-1948*, Harvard Historical Studies, v. 137 (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2000), 158-60.

hierarchy of considerations obviously goes against the purposes of the denazification process, necessity was often cited as reasoning. To balance the need for well-trained medical personnel in a country already lacking with the pressures to thoroughly denazify the population, compromises were put in place that allowed doctors found guilty of Nazi sympathies to be moved to the public sector and restricted from operating their own private practices. Denazification cases involving doctors were asked to be treated with a heightened level of concern and consideration for the availability of doctors in the area. That is, the courts were asked to place a high level of importance not necessarily on the doctors' activities during the war, but rather on their actions and commitment to a democratic system since 1945. Doctors and medical personnel also qualified as part of a "special interest" group and were allowed to go through a special process of appeals.⁶⁰

In a sample compiled by Vogt, it was found that out of over 2.700 completed cases in the denazification courts in various districts, only 287 concerned healthcare workers or doctors to begin with. Of those, 9% of individuals were considered to be "activists" in favour of Nazism. 86% were declared only nominal supporters and given full approval to keep their positions, while the remaining 5% were given conditional approval. Further archival sources also report health and social services as having the highest acceptance rates compared to other professions, suggesting that the Soviet authorities, while banning further sterilisation, were less concerned with the wellbeing of Holocaust survivors who were subject to the procedures.⁶¹

Whether the sterilisation ban was made to establish the Eastern Zone as the place toughest on Nazi law or to discourage any further discussion of either positive or negative eugenics, justice for survivors was not any more of a priority for the Soviets than it was for the Western Powers, nor would it develop any smoother in GDR than in the Federal Republic after the official establishment of the two countries. Additionally, although a trial against key figures of the National Socialist hereditary health tribunal took place under Soviet jurisdiction specifically for sterilisation and crimes against humanity, the sentences given there were later dropped or significantly reduced.⁶² Unlike the Western Zone, there are no large activist groups present in East Germany to represent people who had been sterilised by the Nazis, nor is there any documentation of debates for financial compensation. Rather, the GDR's stance on sterilisation only went as far as outlawing the 1933 sterilisation law "because of its antidemocratic character and its fascist, tendentious

⁶⁰ Vogt, 159.

⁶¹ Vogt, 156–60. Statistics used here appear to be Vogt's own. Other statistics cited in Vogt are lifted from the Brandenburgisches Landeshauptarchiv. See *Denazification in Soviet-Occupied Germany* for more clarification on the collection process and criteria.

⁶² Weindling, "Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization," 192.

presentation of theories about hereditary diseases.”⁶³ The only other statement concerning victims of Nazism with disabilities came in May of 1948, when a group of psychiatrists issued a statement rejecting sterilisation and euthanasia, in which they urged that “medical professionals should work in a social spirit of sacrifice to help ill people.”⁶⁴ No other mentions of disabled people in relation to compensation and Nazism are made, and this statement itself functions in a way that reinforces notions of the disabled body within socialist ideals rather than as citizens who are valuable as individuals.⁶⁵

Individual Attempts to Receive Compensation

Around 400.000 people had been forcibly sterilised under the Nazi regime and a further 300.000 were killed through euthanasia. Over the years, survivors have come out detailing their experiences or those of their loved ones.⁶⁶ Highlighting these stories demonstrates the kinds of excuses that were given by the federal government, as well as the normalisation of their exclusion from post-war justice.

Heinrich Lohne, Compensation for Survivors:

Heinrich Lohne began the process of being recognised as a victim of National Socialism in May of 1985. At the age of ten, Lohne was sent to the Kalemehof Institute for the Disabled, situated in Idstein, Hessen. There, he had worked as a carpenter’s apprentice and was forced to build coffins with unlocking bottoms, with the added responsibility of disposing of corpses. He, like the other residents of the institution, had been starved and beaten by staff during his time there. Lohne reports that towards the end of his time at the institute, he had been forced to dig a grave of his own, and recognising it was meant for himself, survived the war by first rushing to the doctor’s office. When he had realised the doctor would be no help, he escaped to a nearby barn where he had hidden from his oppressors until American troops arrived and liberated the surviving patients of Kalemehof.

Lohne requested status as a victim of National Socialism only so that his forced labour would be recognised as work time to be counted towards his retirement pension. Without it, his

⁶³ Sabine Hanrath, *Zwischen Euthanasie und Psychiatriereform. Anstaltspsychiatrie in Westfalen und Brandenburg: Ein deutsch-deutscher Vergleich, 1945–1964* (Paderborn: Schöningh, 2002), 202, quoted in Carol Poore, *Disability in Twentieth-Century German Culture* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 2007), 252.

⁶⁴ Poore, 251–54.

⁶⁵ For more on disability and socialism, see Poore, “Disability and Socialist Images of the Human Being in the Culture of the German Democratic Republic,” in *Disability in Twentieth-Century German Culture*, 231–72.

⁶⁶ Statistics from the Arbeitsgemeinschaft Bund der „Euthanasie“-Geschädigten und Zwangssterilisierten (BEZ).

monthly payments would be too low to support himself, and Lohne wanted to avoid drawing social assistance. The Hessian state insurance agency rejected Lohne's request on the grounds that he did not qualify under the definitions of Holocaust victims as laid out by the Federal Compensation Act. Additionally, they stated that Lohne had missed the deadline to file compensation anyway. Lohne was never made aware of the initial deadline, or his eligibility status until after it already passed.

In addition to the welfare organisations and the federal body that decides on compensation claims, Lohne caught the attention of the *Idsteiner Zeitung (Idsteiner Newspaper)*, which published his story and the problems he continually faced. In response, the Hessian state welfare organisation, which was responsible for the Kalemehof facility after the war, initially reached out and offered Lohne a one-time payment of 1.000 marks as a kind of 'mercy' for the abuse he faced in the institution and the trouble he had gone through to be compensated after the war. However, they later rescinded this offer, claiming that they were not legally or morally responsible for the damages, mental or physical, inflicted on Heinrich Lohne. Their reasoning? The organisation argued that it did not exist during the war, and it was only established in 1953.

For Heinrich Lohne, the issue was no longer about compensation at this point, but the recognition was denied. While his abusers easily obtained their full pensions, and the city of Idstein strongly campaigned for their pardons, Lohne is haunted both emotionally and physically by what was done to him, without ever being considered part of the persecuted.⁶⁷

Anonymous Citizens, Konstanz, Compensation Attempts by Family Members:

Along with survivors who had been sterilised, children and surviving family members of people killed through the euthanasia program were also excluded from receiving reparations under the criteria of the compensation act. Their attempts to get help through other means were rejected for multiple reasons, as shown by two women from separate families whose parents were killed through the euthanasia program.

In 1983, the city of Konstanz had discovered 193 urns of euthanasia victims in the basement of a local morgue. The surviving family members were searched for and contacted when possible. For one woman, this is how she learned that her mother had been killed in a gas chamber at the Grafeneck facility in 1940. Over 40 years later, the daughter processed the new information given to her and attempted to apply for compensation in March of 1984. The state officials in Baden-Württemberg rejected the application. According to the state compensation office, the

⁶⁷ Ernst Klee, "Geldverschwendung an Schwachsinnige und Säufer," *Die Zeit*, no. 18, April 26, 1986, 2-3.

deadline to file for reparations was at the end of 1969, and since then, they have been unable to file any new cases. The woman attempted to appeal the decision, explaining she had only just learned of her mother's fate, and did not know she had become a victim of National Socialism until 1983 when her mother's ashes were found. The compensation office responded, saying that these reasons were "insignificant," and an exception would not be made for her.⁶⁸

Another woman reports that her family was denied any compensation after her father had been killed in Grafeneck, and that interactions with the authorities continually burden her family emotionally. Her mother first applied for reparations in 1955 after the family escaped to the Federal Republic, but the continued rejections led her to give up entirely on receiving compensation. For the rest of her life, the woman's mother was bothered by the fact that her life and the lives of her children were ruined by National Socialism, and that they lived without recognition. This burden was passed to the daughter, who also failed to receive acknowledgement of their suffering.⁶⁹

In response to issues like this, the Federal Ministry of Finance reasoned that reparations were made to go to victims themselves, and this was impossible to do for victims of euthanasia. However, there was, theoretically, a way around this by filing for hardship compensation through §171, paragraph three, number two of the act. Such a request was only granted if the applicant could prove that they would be receiving financial support from the person who died, had they not been killed or injured by war.⁷⁰ Clearly, this "loophole" does not easily apply to those whose family members were considered "unworthy of life" due to their disabilities. As a result, even people's attempts to find ways to be recognized and compensated on an individual basis were oftentimes in vain.

The attempts made by the citizens described above are only a few of the hundreds of cases that were rejected because either the victim in question or the person applying for reparations did not meet the qualifications to be considered persecuted under National Socialism.⁷¹ The sources make it clear that the reasons given by the Federal Republic were arbitrary and shifted as the situation of the applicant changed. The loophole in place for hardship as it stood at the time reinforced ideas that citizens were only as valuable as the labour that they could produce that would turn into monetary support for their families. Further cases were collected and taken on by BEZ, but most of them were continually rejected. Consequently, despite the small steps that were taken to consider sterilised people for hardship compensation, their efforts to actually receive such

⁶⁸ Klee, 1.

⁶⁹ Klee, 2.

⁷⁰ Klee, 1–2; Bundesentschädigungsgesetz - BEG.

⁷¹ For more examples of individual cases, see Margret Hamm, ed., *Ausgegrenzt! warum? Zwangssterilisierte und Geschädigte der NS-"Euthanasie" in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (Berlin: Metropol, 2017), 177–80.

payments had little to no effect on the lives of survivors, as they often did not receive a positive response. Furthermore, in the rare situation where one did receive hardship pay, the amount was small and showed that victims of sterilisation were not held to the same level of regard as other victims of the Holocaust.

Recognition as a Continuing Issue

Recognition for sterilised victims and the family members of euthanasia victims remains an issue in Germany. The Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring was not repealed until 2007. While the law was never used in Germany after the war, this was the first time that the Bundestag explicitly ruled that it held no power in the country and repealed it entirely. In the session, the law is recognized as Nazi in nature and a component of the racial laws. People with disabilities, both those who are physically and psychologically disabled, are explicitly named as victims for the first time. Ultimately, despite this recognition by individual parties who worked with BEZ, such as the Left and Green parties, people with disabilities are not added to the definition of who is declared a victim of Nazism.⁷²

This is not to suggest that no progress has been made at all. In addition to the various revisions made in the 1980s and 1990s that were discussed earlier in this article, the Bundestag has made amendments throughout the 2000s to the current day. In 2002, children of euthanasia victims were first given the opportunity to apply for a one-time hardship payment of €2.556,46. To file the claim, surviving children needed to provide documentation of their parent's murder, and to have not reached adulthood at the time of the murder. The amendment continued to receive backlash from the League of Persons Damaged by "Euthanasia" and Compulsory Sterilisation, because it was not given with the recognition that the recipients suffered Nazi persecution as the organisation had urged. Instead, the one-time payment was given on the basis that parents had an obligation to provide financial maintenance to their children and were unable to do so because they had been killed.⁷³ Under §844 of the German Social Code, the party responsible for the murder is obligated to pay maintenance to the surviving beneficiaries; this law was the one the German government used as justification to grant payment for the surviving children of euthanasia victims.

⁷² "Plenarprotokoll 16/100, Deutscher Bundestag, Stenografischer Bericht, 100. Sitzung" (Berlin: Deutscher Bundestag, May 24, 2007), 10285.

⁷³ Margret Hamm, ed., *Ausgegrenzt! warum? Zwangssterilisierte und Geschädigte der NS-"Euthanasie" in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (Berlin: Metropol, 2017), 177-80.

In 2011, the hardship clause was retroactively amended from January 27, 2011, in honour of Holocaust Remembrance Day to state that monthly payments may go out to survivors of the euthanasia program. This is a very small group of people, five or ten individuals at the most.⁷⁴ The amendment applies to those who spent at least eighteen months in a euthanasia centre and were still alive at liberation. Given the minimal number of people who meet these criteria, the BEZ mistakenly assumed further payments would also go out to children affected by the murder of their parent(s), but this was not the case. While the criteria for children to receive the one-time hardship payment (€2.556,46) were adjusted to include children who had not yet reached the age of 21 or those who were still students who had not yet reached the age of 27 at the time of their parent's death, applications for ongoing payments for children were denied.⁷⁵ Upon the rejection of applications from the children of euthanasia victims, received only after the applicants provided extensive financial documentation, BEZ released a second press release and sent additional letters to the Bundestag, calling the “symbolic move” a “political stain” and an insult to those who had lost their parents, insisting that the true way to honour the victims of euthanasia would be to compensate the loved ones they left behind.⁷⁶

In 2013, members of the Left and Green parties submitted a series of questions related to previous attempts that were made in relation to considering victims of forced sterilisation, euthanasia victims, and their descendants as victims of the Nazis. In the appeal, the group pointed out that the hardship clause under which survivors and family members were being compensated was intended for damages that were considered general, routine wartime injuries. As such, placing victims of forced sterilisation and euthanasia under this category denotes that their injuries are somewhat “routine” in war and are a possibility to be expected, rather than an act of hatred that was a direct result of Nazi racial legislation. Additionally, they questioned first why Nazi ‘experts’ were invited to make the decision in 1961 when the Compensation Law was still amendable, and

⁷⁴ Margret Hamm, “Pressemitteilung: AKG Härterichtlinienänderung für Euthanasie-Geschädigte: und wieder werden NS Opfer diskriminierend ausgegrenzt” (Arbeitsgemeinschaft Bund der „Euthanasie“-Geschädigten und Zwangssterilisierten, June 8, 2011), https://www.euthanasiegeschadigte-zwangssterilisierte.de/texte-pdf/pm-08-06-2011_web.pdf.

⁷⁵ “Neufassung der Richtlinien der Bundesregierung über Härteleistungen an Opfer von nationalsozialistischen Unrechtsmaßnahmen im Rahmen des Allgemeinen Kriegsfolgengesetzes (AKG-Härterichtlinien)” (Berlin: Deutscher Bundestag, 2011).

⁷⁶ Margret Hamm, “Brief der AG BEZ an die Fraktionsvorsitzenden von CDU/CSU, FDP, SPD, Bündnis 90/DIE GRÜNEN und DIE LINKE. im Deutschen Bundestag zur Umsetzung der AKG Härterichtlinienänderung.,” June 22, 2011, <https://www.euthanasiegeschadigte-zwangssterilisierte.de/dokumente/ag-bez-brief-fraktionsvorsitzende-22-06-11.pdf>; see also Hamm, “Pressemitteilung: AKG Härterichtlinienänderung für Euthanasie-Geschädigte: und wieder werden NS Opfer diskriminierend ausgegrenzt.”

why the government was unwilling to make a law comparable to the original for this victim group if BEG must remain closed.⁷⁷

The questions were answered, but not in a manner that changed the situation for survivors or surviving dependants. Rather than addressing the discrepancies between those with and without recognition through BEG, the government responded that the amount received by survivors under the hardship act was increased in 2011 and that it was impossible to amend the Compensation Act because claims had closed. In response to the possibility of creating new compensation schemes for these groups, the government saw no differences on the political level between receiving payment and recognition through BEG than through the hardship act. They explained that negotiations for reparations that went to other groups were done with international organisations. In particular agreements with the State of Israel was named, along with general regard to other “global agreements with various states, foundations, etc.”⁷⁸ The implication of this statement goes back to the fact that no international bodies in the post-war period were considered the sterilisation of people with disabilities a crime, and the League of Persons Damaged by “Euthanasia” and Compulsory Sterilisation was not established until 1987, eighteen years after the closing of claims under the Federal Compensation Act. Regarding the refusal to add victims of sterilisation and euthanasia to the list of victims in 1961, the response was simply that the Federal Government is prevented from re-evaluating measures taken by the Bundestag, and no political assessment of the experts involved exists.⁷⁹

Since 2013, there has been little development in the situation for victims of sterilisation and euthanasia. The most recent measure passed in 2021 allows for the spouses of surviving Nazi victims to apply for temporary compensation—up to nine months after the survivor’s death—if they were eligible for a pension under the Federal Compensation Act or the General Consequences of War Act, the law which is responsible for paying hardship compensation to victims of euthanasia or sterilisation.⁸⁰ Since this addition, all further changes have been increases to the payment amounts under the hardship clause of the General Consequences of War Act.

⁷⁷ “Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Ulla Jelpke, Dr. Ilja Seifert, Jan Korte, weiterer Abgeordneter und der Fraktion Die Linke. Entschädigungsleistungen für „Euthanasie“-Geschädigte und Zwangssterilisierte” (Deutscher Bundestag, February 19, 2013), <https://dip.bundestag.de/vorgang/entsch%C3%A4digungsleistungen-f%C3%BCr-euthanasie-gesch%C3%A4digte-und-zwangssterilisierte-nachfrage-zur-antwort-der-bundesregierung/50699>.

⁷⁸ “Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Ulla Jelpke, Dr. Ilja Seifert, Jan Korte, weiterer Abgeordneter und der Fraktion Die Linke.”

⁷⁹ “Entschädigungsleistungen für „Euthanasie“-Geschädigte und Zwangssterilisierte,” 5–6.

⁸⁰ “Richtlinie der Bundesregierung über Übergangsleistungen an hinterbliebene Ehegatten von NS-Opfern” *Bundesamt für zentrale Dienste und offene Vermögensfragen* (BADV), March 31, 2021), <https://www.badv.bund.de/DE/OffeneVermögensfragen/UebergangsleistungenEhegattenNSOpfer/start.html>.

With the latest developments, it seems that victims of euthanasia and forced sterilisation will remain under the class of victims who have had ‘general’ injuries due to war, rather than receiving their full recognition as victims of Nazi plans to ‘cleanse’ the nation of the sick and disabled. As of 2023, their payments have been increased to 600 Euros per month, but the changes made throughout the years came much too late to have an impact for significant numbers of people. As of December 31, 2022, the League of Persons Damaged by “Euthanasia” and Compulsory Sterilisation reports that only 29 victims of forced sterilisation are alive and eligible, along with one survivor of the euthanasia policies.⁸¹ The League continues to host conferences and projects relating to the exclusion of people with disabilities from post-war justice, but the progress that has been made is far too late. The vast majority of victims died without receiving any recognition of their suffering, and for those who died before 2007, in a country that still considered the law responsible for their suffering a routine health precaution rather than discrimination.

To this day, no official apologies have been made by the German government for the crimes committed against people with disabilities or their surviving family members. The only organisation to apologise thus far has been the German Medical Association, whose members not only committed crimes and participated in human experimentation during the Nazi times, but also used body parts harvested from victims for scientific study until the 1990s, sometimes longer.⁸² The apology, issued in 2012, was too late to be received by the people who deserved it, but is a welcome starting point for the recognition of these victims. As organisations previously involved in Nazi crimes finally shift from positions of denial to remorse, an opportunity is left open for the German government itself to finally recognize further groups of victims who were previously left unacknowledged. Further, the current state of research makes it clear that there is a massive disparity between scholarship on post-war justice in West and East Germany that is waiting to be filled.

Lastly, as this article has pointed out, the responsibility of justice for victims of sterilisation lies not with Germany alone, but also with the multitude of nations who have failed to acknowledge their eugenic practices of the past and offer some apologies or reparations to the surviving victims.

⁸¹ Hamm, *Ausgegrenzt! warum?*, 177–180.

⁸² Stephan Kolb, Paul Weindling, Volker Roelcke, and Horst Seithe, “Apologising for Nazi Medicine: A Constructive Starting Point,” *Lancet* 380, no. 9843 (August 25, 2012): 722–23.

Bibliography

Primary Sources

“2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung. Bonn, Donnerstag, den 7. Februar 1957.” Deutscher Bundestag, 1957.

“Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Ulla Jelpke, Dr. Ilja Seifert, Jan Korte, weiterer Abgeordneter und der Fraktion DIE LINKE. Entschädigungsleistungen für „Euthanasie“-Geschädigte und Zwangssterilisierte.” Deutscher Bundestag, February 19, 2013.

<https://dip.bundestag.de/vorgang/entsch%C3%A4digungsleistungen-f%C3%BCr-euthanasie-gesch%C3%A4digte-und-zwangssterilisierte-nachfrage-zur-antwort-der-bundesregierung/50699>.

Bundesministerium der Justiz, and Bundesamt für Justiz. Bundesgesetz zur Entschädigung für Opfer der Nationalsozialistischen Verfolgung (Bundesentschädigungsgesetz - BEG) (1953).

Goldman, Ari L. “Upheaval in the East: East Germany; East Germany Agrees to Pay Reparations to the Jewish Victims of the Nazis,” *The New York Times*, February 9, 1990.

“Brief der AG BEZ an die Fraktionvorsitzenden von CDU/CSU, FDP, SPD, Bündnis 90/DIE GRÜNEN und DIE LINKE. im Deutschen Bundestag zur Umsetzung der AKG Härterichtlinienänderung,” June 22, 2011. <https://www.euthanasiegeschaeDIGte-zwangssterilisierte.de/dokumente/ag-bez-brief-fraktionsvorsitzende-22-06-11.pdf>.

“Pressemitteilung: AKG Härterichtlinienänderung für Euthanasie-Geschädigte: Und wieder werden NS Opfer diskriminierend ausgegrenzt.” Arbeitsgemeinschaft Bund der „Euthanasie“-Geschädigten und Zwangssterilisierten, June 8, 2011. https://www.euthanasiegeschaeDIGte-zwangssterilisierte.de/texte-pdf/pm-08-06-2011_web.pdf.

ICRC Database, Treaties, States Parties and Commentaries, “Agreement for the Prosecution and Punishment of the Major War Criminals of the European Axis, and Charter of the International Military Tribunal.” (London, August 8, 1945).

<https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/nuremberg-tribunal-charter-1945/article-6b>.

Klee, Ernst. “Geldverschwendung an Schwachsinnige und Säufer,” *Die Zeit*, no. 18, April 26, 1986.

Neufassung der Richtlinien der Bundesregierung über Härteleistungen an Opfer von nationalsozialistischen Unrechtsmaßnahmen im Rahmen des Allgemeinen Kriegsfolgengesetzes (AKG-Härterichtlinien) (2011).

“Plenarprotokoll 16/100, Deutscher Bundestag, Stenografischer Bericht, 100. Sitzung.” Deutscher Bundestag, May 24, 2007.

“Protokoll der 34. Sitzung des Ausschusses für Wiedergutmachung.” Deutscher Bundestag, April 13, 1961.

“Richtlinie der Bundesregierung über Übergangsleistungen an hinterbliebene Ehegatten von NS-Opfern.” Bundesamt für zentrale Dienste und offene Vermögensfragen (BADV), March 31, 2021. <https://www.badv.bund.de/DE/OffeneVermögensfragen/UebergangsleistungenEhegattenNSOpfer/start.html>.

Secondary Sources

Adams, Mark B., ed. *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*, Monographs on the History and Philosophy of Biology. New York: Oxford University Press, 1990.

Binding, Karl, and Alfred Hoche. *Die Freigabe der Vernichtung lebensunwerten Lebens: ihr Mass und ihr Ziel (1920)*. Berlin: Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag, 2006.

Black, Edwin. *War against the Weak: Eugenics and America's Campaign to Create a Master Race*. New York: Four Walls Eight Windows, 2003.

Brody, Howard and M. Wayne Cooper. “Binding and Hoche’s ‘Life Unworthy of Life:’ A Historical and Ethical Analysis.” *Perspectives in Biology and Medicine* 57, no. 4 (2014): 500–511. <https://doi.org/10.1353/pbm.2014.0042>.

Klautke, Egbert. “‘The Germans Are Beating Us at Our Own Game’: American Eugenics and the German Sterilization Law of 1933.” *History of the Human Sciences* 29, no. 3 (July 2016): 25–43. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952695116631230>.

Friedlander, Henry. *The Origins of Nazi Genocide: From Euthanasia to the Final Solution*. Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press, 1995.

Hamm, Margret, ed. *Ausgegrenzt! warum? Zwangssterilisierte und Geschädigte der NS-"Euthanasie" in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland*. Berlin: Metropol, 2017.

Hirsch, Francine. *Soviet Judgment at Nuremberg: A New History of the International Military Tribunal after World War II*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2020.

Hyatt, Stephanie. “A Shared History of Shame: Sweden’s Four-Decade Policy of Forced Sterilization and the Eugenics Movement in the United States.” *Indiana International & Comparative Law Review* 8, no. 2 (1998): 475–503. <https://doi.org/10.18060/17816>.

Kolb, Stephan, Paul Weindling, Volker Roelcke, and Horst Seithe. “Apologising for Nazi Medicine: A Constructive Starting Point.” *Lancet* 380, no. 9843 (August 25, 2012): 722–23. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(12\)61396-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(12)61396-8).

Meloni, Maurizio. *Political Biology: Science and Social Values in Human Heredity from Eugenics to Epigenetics*. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2016.

Nettl, John P. *The Eastern Zone and Soviet Policy in Germany, 1945–50*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1951.

Poore, Carol. *Disability in Twentieth-Century German Culture*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 2007.

Sands, Philippe. *East West Street: On the Origins of “Genocide” and “Crimes against Humanity.”* New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 2016.

Simpson, John. “Chapter 2: What’s in a Name?” In *Supporting Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities & Mental Illness*, edited by Cathy McPhalen, 8–18. Vancouver: BCcampus, 2015.

Timm, Angelika. *Jewish Claims Against East Germany*. Budapest: Central European University Press, 1998.

Vogt, Timothy R. *Denazification in Soviet-Occupied Germany: Brandenburg, 1945–1948*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2000.

Weindling, Paul. “Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization.” In *Psychiatry and the Legacies of Eugenics: Historical Studies of Alberta and Beyond*, edited by Frank W. Stahnisch and Erna Kurbegović, 181–98. Edmonton: Athabasca University Press, 2020.